

Studies on synthesis and coordination chemistry of catechol based phosphine oxides

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Abstract : Two different types of catechol based phosphine oxides are prepared by the condensation reaction of phenyldichloro phosphine oxide and the corresponding catechol derivatives in the presence of triethylamine. These compounds are used for the preparation of their corresponding La^{III} and Th^{IV} complexes. All these products were characterized by spectroscopic data.

Keywords : Phosphine oxide, catechol, stability and coordination behavior.

Introduction

Pentavalent phosphine oxides are one of the important classes of compounds in both organic as well as inorganic chemistry as they were used as reagents in organic synthesis, powerful ligands in *f*-metal coordination chemistry and extraction studies, catalysts and bioactive compounds^{1,2}. There is always a constant demand for the designing and synthesis of novel phosphine oxides for the selective separation of actinides and lanthanides from radioactive nuclear waste³. In this context, the present work describes the synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of catechol based phosphine oxides [eq. (1)].

Aldrich) PhPOCl₂, catechol (Avra Chemicals), tertiary butylcatechol (Thomas Baker) was used as received and the other reagents (Merck) like triethylamine was dried by using Na metal. Hydrated rare earth metal nitrate and chloride salts (SD Fine and Loba), Th(NO₃)₄·5H₂O and LaCl₃·7H₂O were used as received.

¹H, ¹³C and ³¹P{¹H}-NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 400 MHz, Model : ASCEND and all ¹H chemical shifts are reported relative to the residual proton resonance in deuterated solvents (all at 298 K, CDCl₃). Infrared spectra were recorded on Shimadzu, IR Affinity-1 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometer. Gas

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All the manipulations were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere (inert) using Schlenk line technique. All the commercially available solvents were distilled from Na metal/benzophenone. The phosphorus reagents (Sigma-

chromatography and Mass analyses were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer Clarus 680 C Gas Chromatograph and Perkin-Elmer Clarus 600 C Mass Spectrometer.

General procedure for synthesis of ligands 3 and 4 :

4.72 g of catechol (42.9 mmol), 24.0 mL of Et₃N (171.6 mmol) and 50 mL of dry toluene were taken in a

two neck RB flask equipped with condenser and dropping funnel. A solution of 4.7 g PhPOCl₂ (42.9 mmol, 6.34 mL) in 50 mL of dry THF was taken in the dropping funnel and added to the contents of the flask under N₂ atmosphere over a period of 30 min under ice bath. After the complete addition, the reaction mixture was refluxed at 120 °C for 24 h using an oil bath under constant stirring. The white precipitate (Et₃N.HCl) formed during the reaction was removed by filtration and a brown coloured semisolid was obtained in quantitative yield as the major product (**3**). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ) : 6.52–7.76 (m, Ph); ³¹P{¹H}-NMR (CDCl₃, δ) : 16.07; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1263 (P=O); (EI-Mass) M⁺ : 232.2.

A similar procedure was followed for the preparation of **4** was used by taking 4.25 g of *t*-Bu-catechol (25.6 mmol), 3.8 mL of PhPOCl₂ (25.6 mmol, 5 g) and 14.4 mL of Et₃N (102.4 mmol, 10.36 g). The pale brown oily mass was obtained in quantitative yield and the product was identified as **4**. ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ) : 6.90–7.27 (8H, m, Ph) and 1.22 (9H, s, *t*-Bu); ³¹P{¹H}-NMR (CDCl₃, δ) : 16.13; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1203 (P=O); (EI-

mL of dichloromethane solvent and this mixture was stirred at room temperature for overnight. The obtained pale yellow precipitate was filtered by using Whatmann filter paper and washed with chloroform to remove any excess of free ligand. The remaining pale yellow solid residue was dried under high vacuum for 4 h and it was found to be **6**. Yield : 83.6% (0.41 g), m.p. 260 °C (dec.); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1201 (P=O). Complex **7** was prepared by following above mentioned procedure by taking 0.78 g of **4** (2.7 mmol) and 0.334 g of LaCl₃·7H₂O (0.9 mmol). Yield of pale yellow solid : 87.8% (0.87 g), m.p. 156 °C (dec.); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1192 (P=O).

The complexes **8** and **9** were also prepared in a same procedure by taking 1 : 2 metal to ligand ratio. Complex **8**, 0.25 g of **3** (1.056 mmol) and 0.30 g of Th(NO₃)₄·5H₂O (0.529 mmol). Yield of pale yellow solid : 87.8% (0.87 g), m.p. 270 °C (dec.); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1180 (P=O). Complex **9**, 0.55 g of **4** (1.89 mmol) and 0.534 g of Th(NO₃)₄·5H₂O (0.95 mmol). Yield of pale yellow solid : 86.6% (0.858 g), m.p. 166 °C (dec.); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1143 (P=O).

Scheme 1

Mass) M⁺ : 288.190. When the reaction was carried out in wet toluene, one of the known products was isolated as **5** (M⁺, 281.2) along with **4**.

General procedure for synthesis of metal complexes **6** :

All the metal complexes (**6-9**) reported in the present work (Scheme 1) were prepared by adopting the following procedure.

In a RB flask, 0.37 g of **3** (1.588 mmol) and 0.196 g of LaCl₃·7H₂O (0.529 mmol) (3 : 1) were charged in 10

Results and discussion

The synthesis of precursor molecules **3** and **4** were synthesized by the condensation reaction of phenyldichloro phosphine oxide and the corresponding catechol derivatives (**1** and **2**) in the presence of triethylamine. The reactions were monitored by ³¹P NMR data. The structures of these ligands were confirmed by spectroscopic and mass data. In the presence of moisture, the reaction showed a hydrolysis product, **5** as shown in eq. (2). The formed

by-product **5** was separated from **4** by column chromatography using a solvent mixture (30% CH₂Cl₂ in petroleum ether). The formation of metal complexes (**6-9**) was confirmed by FT-IR data. The presumed structures are given in Chart 1 according to the literature reports^{4,5}.

Chart 1. Predicted structures of **6-9**.

Conclusion

Catechol based phosphine oxides were prepared by the condensation reaction of phenyldichloro phosphine oxide and the corresponding catechol derivatives. The corresponding La^{III} and Th^{IV} complexes were prepared and isolated in pure form. All these products were characterized by spectroscopic analysis.

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